

Analysis of Artificial Intelligence Policies for Higher Education in Europe: Country reports

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ABSTRACT

This document presents the country reports that were used as the basis for the analysis of 15 AI policies for higher education from eight European countries, drawn from individual universities, from consortia of universities and from government agencies. The results of this analysis are published in a journal paper.

This journal paper focuses the comparison of different aspects among the selected AI policies based on an overview of current research findings. The analysis distinguishes between four potential target groups, namely students, teachers, education managers and policy makers. The paper aims at contributing to the further development and improvement of AI policies for higher education through the identification of commonalities and gaps within the existing AI policies. Moreover, it calls for further and in particular evidence-based research to identify the potential and practical impact of AI in higher education and highlights the need to combine AI use in (higher) education with education about AI, often called as AI literacy.

KEYWORDS

AI literacy, Artificial Intelligence in education, European countries comparison, Higher Education research, Policy development

I. INTRODUCTION

OUR study aims to analyse policies on AI in higher education. This study is purposely conducted at an early stage in AI policy development, which is characterised by a lack of uniformity within and across the different levels of policy making. The domain is characterised by rather disparate initiatives and varying levels of maturity. This study aims to collect and analyse important themes and to highlight emerging directions in current practice, to set the ground for future consolidation and consensus making.

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Our research questions are “What aspects are addressed in the selected AI policies?” and “How do the policies differ in relation to issuers and target groups?”.

The journal paper [1] performs a formal and content-related analysis of currently published European AI policies for higher education through case study methodology.

For our study, we selected the countries of all co-authors as basis for our research. We have identified and collected AI policies from universities as well as from national public authorities. To keep a balance between the countries, we have selected a national AI policy, if available, and AI policies from universities so that there are not more than four AI policies from each country. To avoid an amount of

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AI policies that we could not handle and analyse, we have selected and concentrated on AI policies that are from larger universities and already in practice for a longer time. The following Table I provides an overview of the analysis categories for each AI policy.

The Table I will be added after final acceptance of the journal paper.

Table II presents the selected 15 AI policies from eight countries:

The Table II will be added after final acceptance of the journal paper.

In the following, we present the country reports that were developed

The country reports will be added after final acceptance of the journal paper.

REFERENCES

[1] Reference will be added after the publication of the journal paper